

A Case Study on Absenteeism of Workers in Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt. Ltd

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ABSTRACT

Employee absenteeism has been a growing concern to employers. Absenteeism may lead to financial losses and thereby resulting reduction in productivity and the costs of sick leave benefits paid as wages for no work. This project on Employee Absenteeism reveals that one of the major problems is absenteeism. Absenteeism is the practice or habit of being an absentee and an absentee is one who habitually stays away from work. Employees Absenteeism is a serious problem for management because it involves heavy additional expenses. Absenteeism hinders planning, production, efficiency and functioning of the organization. In fact high rates of absenteeism affect an organization state of health and also supervisory and managerial effectiveness.

Keywords: Absenteeism, Performance, Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Absenteeism has been variously defined authorities from time to time. Thus the term absenteeism refers to the worker's absence from his regular task when he is scheduled to work. Any employee may stay away from work if he has taken leave to which he is entitled or as the ground of sickness or some accident without any previous sanction of leave. Nevertheless usually involuntary layoff, lack of work, authorized leave or vacation period of work stoppage is not counted as absence strikes and lockouts are treated as absence are many include late attendance in it.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the rate of absenteeism in coca-cola beverages pvt ltd.,

- To identify the variables that lead to absenteeism.
- To Study the variables that reduces the rate of absenteeism.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Study of absenteeism among industrial workers is not only from view point but it is important from the view point of the moral of the employees. Even though the effect of the good moral of the employee, may not be evaluated in terms of costs, but it should be say that it is important than cost. The main purpose behind this project is to find out the causes that lead to Absenteeism.

LIMITATIONS

- The worker's name is mentioned in questionnaire while collecting the data, this might have been a negative approach in their view.
- Because of their busy schedule the data is collected in permitted area.
- To collect the information superiors are not interested, because they are feeling work may disturb.

DATA COLLECTION

Data collected from primary and secondary sources.

➤ Primary data

Primary data collected through questionnaires, observation and personal interview.

➤ Secondary data

Secondary data collected through reference books and past records and absenteeism reports of the company.

➤ Sample Size : 50

PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

After the data have been collected it has to be analyzed. The data obtained from the questionnaire is arranged in a serial order then a master copy with tabulation method is being prepared. Tabulation is a part of the technical procedure where in the essential data are put in the form of tables.

CALCULATION OF ABSENTEEISM RATE

The absenteeism rate is a statistical expression of the total time lost due to the unauthorized absence during a particular period.

The standard formula to calculate the rate of absenteeism is the ratio of man shifts lost due to absence of workers to the number of man shifts scheduled to work.

$$\text{Absenteeism percentage rate} = \frac{\text{Man - Shifts lost due to absent}}{\text{Man - Shifts scheduled to work}} \times 100$$

$$1. \text{ Spell of Absence} = \frac{\text{Number of absents in a year}}{\text{Average number employed in the year}} \times 100$$

$$2. \text{ Absenteeism percentage rate} = \frac{\text{Number of employee's days lost through out job absence during the period}}{\text{Average number of employees} \times \text{number of work days}} \times 100$$

According to FLIPPO
$$\text{Absenteeism\%} = \frac{\text{Man - days lost}}{\text{Man - days scheduled to work}} \times 100$$

TABLE – 1 DISTANCE BETWEEN RESPONDENTS HOUSE AND FACTORY

Distance	Respondents	Percentage
Below 1 km	20	40
1 to 5 km	5	10
5 to 10 km	8	16
Above 10 km	17	34
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

k.m. distance, 10% of respondents are residing in 1 to 5 k.m. distance, 16% of respondents are residing in 5 to 10 k.m. distance, and 34% of respondents are residing above 10 k.m. distance.

TABLE – 2 ABSENT DUE TO UNEXPECTED WORK

Unexpected Work	Respondents	Percentage
RARELY	19	38
Some times	10	20
Always	0	0
Never	21	42
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 40% of respondents are residing below 1

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The above table represents that from the total respondents, 38% of respondents are absent rarely due to unexpected work, 20% of respondents are absent sometimes due to unexpected work, and 42% of respondents are never absent due to unexpected work.

TABLE – 3 HEALTH IS THE REASON FOR ABSENT

Health Is Reason	Respondents	Percentage
Rarely	15	30
Some times	23	46
Always	0	0
Never	12	24
TOTAL	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 30% of respondents are absent due to ill health, 46% of respondents are absent sometimes due to ill health, and 24% of respondents are never absent due to ill health.

TABLE – 4 ABSENT DUE TO LATE COMING

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Sometimes	5	10
Always	2	4
Rarely	18	36
Never	25	50
TOTAL	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents, 10% of respondents are sometimes absent due to late coming, 4% of respondents are always absent due to late coming, 36 of respondents are rarely absent due to late coming and 50% of respondents are never absent due to late coming.

TABLE – 5 DIFFERENT PROBLEMS FACING TO ATTEND DUTY

Problems	Respondents	Percentage
Sickness	19	38
Social	12	24
Personal	19	38
TOTAL	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 38% are facing sickness problem, 24% are facing social problem, and 38% are facing personal problems.

TABLE – 6 EMPLOYEES MODE OF TRANSPORT

Mode of Transport	Respondents	Percentage
BY BUS	26	52
By bicycle	7	14
By Scooter	13	26
On foot	4	8
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents, 52% of respondents are coming by bus, 14% of respondents are coming by bicycle, 26% of respondents are coming by scooter and 8% of respondents are coming on foot.

TABLE – 7 ABSENTEEISM AFFECTS THE ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF WORKERS

Economic Conditions	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	35	70
Agree	15	30
Disagree	00	0
Strongly disagree	00	0
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 70% of respondents are strongly agree that absenteeism affects the economic conditions, 30% of respondents are agree that absenteeism affects the economic conditions.

TABLE – 8 ABSENT DUE TO HEAVY WORK LOAD

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Sometimes	12	24
Always	3	6
Rarely	29	58
Never	6	12
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 24% of respondents are sometimes absent due to heavy work load, 6% of respondents are always absent due to heavy work load, 58% of respondents are rarely absent due to heavy work load and 12% of respondents are never absent due to heavy work load.

TABLE –9 FEELING BOREDOM IN DOING THE ASSIGNED JOB

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Rarely	16	32
Sometimes	14	28
Always	0	0
Never	20	40
TOTAL	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents, 32% of respondents are rarely feeling boredom, 28% of respondents are sometimes feeling boredom, and 40% of respondents are never felt boredom in doing the assigned job.

TABLE – 9EMPLOYEES SATISFACTION REGARDING SAFETY MEASURES

Satisfaction	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	35	70
Agree	10	20
Disagree	3	6
Strongly disagree	2	4
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 70% of respondents are strongly agree about the safety measures provided, 20% of respondents above the safety measures provided, 6% of respondents are disagree about the safety measures provided and 4% of respondents are strongly disagree about the safety measures provided.

TABLE –10 RESPONDENTS HAVING ANY OTHER SOURCES OF INCOME

Sources of Income	Respondents	Percentage
Agriculture	13	26
Business	8	16
Nothing else	29	58
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 26% of respondents are having agriculture as sources of income, 16% of respondents are having business as sources of income, and 58% of respondents are not having any other sources of income

TABLE – 11 WORKERS FACING PROBLEM IN SHIFTS

Shift	Respondents	Percentage
1 st shift	7	14
2 nd shift	6	12
3 rd shift	29	58
General	8	16
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table represents that from the total respondents 14% are facing problem in 1st shift, 12% of respondents are facing problem in 2nd shift, 50% of respondents are facing problem in 3rd shift, and 16% of respondents are facing problems in general shift.

FINDINGS

From the study it has been found that there are many factors including that workers absenteeism, some of them are as follows.

- Absenteeism in shifts is mainly in third shift i.e., 10 p.m. to 6 a.m. that means it is high in night shifts. So workers in the night shift experience greater discomfort during their course of work than they do during daytime.
- From the samples of the workers, some of the workers are debited, other workers in work place due to which they absent themselves in order to escape the creditors.
- Some may absent because of ill health, family member’s health and unexpected work etc.
- Most of the employees facing personal problems. It is also reason for absenteeism.
- Some of the workers strongly agree that they have cordial relationship with their higher authorities.
- Some of the workers absent because there are having other sources of income i.e., agriculture, business etc.

SUGGESTIONS

The following are some of the suggestions in order to minimize absenteeism in the company.

- Many of the workers agree that they have good relationship with higher authorities. Some may fear to talk with them, improving the communication network particularly the upward communication.
- By providing high wages and allowances based on organizational, financial positions.

- By providing proper loans in order to satisfy the workers need. The company may reduce the absenteeism rate.
- Selecting the workers by testing them thoroughly recording their aspirators, value system, and sense of responsibility.
- Selecting the workers who do not have any other sources of income i.e., agriculture and business etc.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the information and analysis we finally conclude that absenteeism very much evident in coca-cola company on the basis of many factors involved such as Health issues, boredom, lack of transportation facilities, lack of motivation, no proper measures taken to resolve the employee issues at an appropriate time, lack of job satisfaction and finally employees looking for green postures for their social and economic well being.

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